

Electromechanics of a Collection of Current Carrying Cantilevered Fibers Sliding against a Plane Moving Surface in a Three Dimensional Magnetic Field

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Abstract— This paper builds on a previously developed model which describes the electromechanical behavior of a single, cantilevered current carrying fiber with arbitrary physical orientation relative to a moving surface in a three dimensional arbitrary magnetic field. In the present paper we extend that model to a collection of similar fibers spatially separated along the moving surface. The collection of fibers carries a transport current and an external mechanical force is applied to the sum of the fibers to keep their free ends in electrical contact with the moving surface. The contact resistance is an inverse function of the load and depends on whether the contact spots are elastic or plastic. A frictional force on the fibers in the direction of motion results. Furthermore, since the current carrying fibers are in the presence of a 3 component arbitrary magnetic field, a distributed Lorentz force along the length of an individual fiber exists which distorts the shape of the fibers and changes the individual contact load and contact resistance while keeping the sum of the loads the same. Furthermore, since the moving surface is cutting net flux, there exist different potentials at different fibers and circulating currents between these fibers result. These circulating currents are of different magnitudes and in opposite directions in individual fibers thus adding or subtracting from the transport current while keeping the total transport current the same. As a result of the circulating currents, the Lorentz forces are modified and the individual contact loads and resistances change while keeping the total mechanical load on and total transport current through all the fibers constant. This leads to a distorted current and mechanical load profile in the collection of fibers. For a given constant magnetic field and direction of moving surface, the direction of transport current results in differing distributions of current and mechanical load profile. Examples are presented.

I. INTRODUCTION

In a previous internal investigation¹ we derived the formalism for analyzing the electromechanics of a single, current carrying fiber sliding against a plane in the presence of a large magnetic field of arbitrary orientation. In that study, which incorporated results found in previous studies²⁻⁷, the current and the mechanical contact force at the fiber tip-slider interface are specified and do not change but the fiber itself, changes shape, deflects and the applied electric potential necessary to drive the current varies with conditions such as slider speed and differing magnetic field conditions. We

discovered a bifurcation in the solution space of such fibers which leads to a history dependant equilibrium condition.

In the present paper we have extended that investigation to include a collection of fibers which carry a constant total transport current and are held against the slider by a constant total force. The currents and tip forces of the individual fibers are allowed to vary, but the sum over the fibers remains constant. The purpose of this model is to generate base-state results for comparison to the results from future models which will include effects that are neglected here. As examples, (1) the present model assumes that there is no wear, while a future model will include the change in length of each fiber due to the wear at its tip, and (2) the present model uses a simple variation of the contact resistance with the normal force between the fiber tip and the rotor surface, while a future model will include variations of the contact resistance with a number of other variables. This initial model uses the single fiber model which is presented in Reference 1. The combination of the present brush model with those future single-fiber models will generate other extensions of the present basic brush model.

II. ASSUMPTIONS

We assume that the slider (e.g. a rotor) and fixed (e.g. stator) surfaces are planar and are parallel to each other. For the single-fiber model, we assumed that the rotor surface is effectively planar over the distance traveled by one fiber tip for all operational conditions. In the present study we assume that the rotor surface is planar over the length and breadth of the brush, which is a somewhat stronger assumption. Figure 1a, from reference 1, shows a free body diagram of the forces acting on an arbitrary cross-section of a single fiber and the fiber tip. Figure 1b presents simple graphical representation of the collection of fibers and the rotor-stator system of the present study. Finally, Figure 1c depicts the deformation of two sample fibers located at differing positions in the row of fibers, the distortion resulting from carrying differing currents, both magnitude and direction, in the applied magnetic field.

For the brush model, we use a Cartesian coordinate system with the y axis perpendicular to the rotor and stator surfaces, with the x axis in the direction of the rotor velocity, i.e., in the azimuthal direction, and with the origin at the center of the base of brush at the stator surface. We assume that the

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undeformed brush has a rectangular cross section. For the base of the brush at the stator surface, $-L_x \leq x \leq L_x, -L_z \leq z \leq L_z$, where $2L_x$ is the azimuthal dimension of the brush and $2L_z$ is the axial dimension of the brush for a radially oriented brush or the radial dimension for an axially oriented brush.

Figure 1 . a) Tip and distributed EM Forces on Individual Fiber from Ref. 1. b) Row of fibers attached to fixed base with tips contacting sliding surface c) Example of two fibers displaying deformations resulting from transporting differing currents in the applied magnetic field.

The single-fiber model uses a local Cartesian coordinate system for each fiber with the origin at the root of the fiber at the stator surface. Since the single-fiber model is used in the present brush model, we need the relationships between the brush coordinates and the local fiber coordinates. If the root of a given fiber is located at $(x_0, 0, z_0)$ in the brush coordinate system, then

$$x_{brush} = x_0 + x_{fiber}, \quad y_{brush} = y_{fiber}, \quad z_{brush} = z_0 + z_{fiber}, \quad (1a-c)$$

where $x_{brush}, y_{brush}, z_{brush}$ are the brush coordinates for the centerline of this fiber, while $x_{fiber}, y_{fiber}, z_{fiber}$ are the local coordinates for this fiber in the single-fiber model. Through all of this paper except the Results section, x, y, z will denote the brush coordinates. In the Results section, all of the results for the entire brush involve the dimensional brush coordinates x, y, z , while all of the results for a single fiber involve the dimensionless, local fiber coordinates x, y, z , normalized by the length L of the fiber.

We assume that all the fibers in the brush have the same length L , the same diameter d , the same elastic modulus E , and the same electrical resistivity, ρ_e . We also assume that all the undeformed fibers are parallel. In other words, all fibers have the same values of θ_0 and α_0 , where θ_0 is the angle between the undeformed fiber and \hat{x} , while α_0 is the angle between the projection of the undeformed fiber onto the y - z plane and \hat{y} . Here $\hat{x}, \hat{y}, \hat{z}$ are unit vectors for both sets of Cartesian coordinates.

We assume that the bending stresses in all the fibers are less than the yield stress, so that all deformations are elastic. We assume that the fibers do not touch each other. The first consequence of this assumption is that there are no contact forces between fibers. (A subsequent model, to be published later, incorporates fiber-fiber interactions and shows that

although contact and forces can exist between some of the tips of the fibers, the overall effect on contact resistance and friction is minimal). The second consequence is that there is no direct flow of electric current between fibers, so that the electric current I through a given fiber is the same over the entire length of this fiber. We assume that the magnetic field, $\mathbf{B} = B_x \hat{x} + B_y \hat{y} + B_z \hat{z}$, is uniform over the entire volume occupied by the brush. In the single-fiber model, we assumed that \mathbf{B} is uniform over the length of each fiber, so that our brush assumption is stronger. However, it would be relatively easy to modify the present brush model to treat a magnetic field which varies with either x or z across the brush, but which is effectively uniform over the length of each fiber. A good example would be the variation of the azimuthal component of the magnetic field B_x with z due to the electric current through the brush.

We assume that the only forces on each fiber are the tip force, $\mu N \hat{x} - N \hat{y}$, and the distributed electromagnetic body force per unit of fiber length, $(\hat{t}) \times \mathbf{B}$. Here μ is the coefficient of sliding friction, N is the normal force between the fiber tip and the rotor surface, and \hat{t} is the local unit vector which is tangent to the centerline of a fiber at each point along the fiber from its root at the stator surface to its tip at the rotor surface. We also assume that the tips of the fibers remain in contact with the rotor surface at all times and are held in place by a spring force applied to the base of the brush.

Other assumptions are presented in the problem formulation.

III. ELECTRICAL RESISTANCES

We assume that the rotor and stator are perfect electrical conductors, i.e., their electrical resistivities are effectively zero. Since the stator does not move, the electric potential function ϕ is uniform in the stator. We use the stator voltage as the datum, so that $\phi=0$ in the stator. Since the rotor moves with a constant uniform velocity V_x and since there is a uniform magnetic field, there is a linear variation of ϕ in the rotor. At the rotor surface, $\phi = \phi_0 + V_x B_y z$, where ϕ_0 is the voltage difference across the center of the brush. The value of ϕ_0 is determined by the condition that the sum of the electric currents through all of the fibers must equal the specified transport current, I_{trans} .

The electrical resistance of each fiber is in series with the contact resistance for the gap between the fiber tip and the rotor surface. The resistance of the fiber is $\rho_e L / \pi R^2$, where $R = d/2$ is the radius of each fiber. Reference 2 presented a formula for the contact resistance of the entire brush times its cross sectional area,

$$R_c A_b = \frac{3.4 \times 10^{-9} [\Omega m^2]}{K^2 f \beta^{2/3}}. \quad (2)$$

Here $\beta = p / p_{trans}$, where p is the normal force per unit area across the interface between the brush and the rotor surface, while p_{trans} is the value of p for the elastic-plastic transition of the contact point on each fiber tip. Equation (2) assumes that the contact spot is elastic, $\beta < 1$. Reference 2 defined f as the fiber volume fraction. However, it was assumed that the undeformed fibers are perpendicular to the rotor surface, i.e., $\theta_0 = \pi/2, \alpha_0 = 0$, while we also want to treat undeformed fibers with other orientations. The only role of f is the determination of the number of fiber contacts per unit area of the rotor surface, n^* . Reference 2 used the formula $n^* = f / \pi R^2$, while the formula which is valid for all undeformed-fiber orientations is

$$n^* = \frac{v_f \sin \theta_0 \cos \alpha_0}{\pi R^2}, \quad (3)$$

where we use v_f to denote the fiber volume fraction. Thus we substitute $f = v_f \sin \theta_0 \cos \alpha_0$ into the formulas of Reference 2. Reference 2 presented the formula

$$K^2 = 1 + 7[\mu m] / (\beta^{2/3} d) \quad (4)$$

as a correction which we set $K^2 = 1$ to avoid finite resistance when β (load) is 0. Therefore the equation we use for the brush contact resistance times brush area is

$$R_c A_b = \frac{3.4 \times 10^{-9} [\Omega m^2]}{v_f \sin \theta_0 \cos \alpha_0 \beta^{2/3}}. \quad (5)$$

Reference 2 gave the value $p_{trans} = 1.5 \times 10^5 f [Pa]$ for copper fibers, and we use this value with $f = v_f \sin \theta_0 \cos \alpha_0$.

Reference 2 treated brushes with uniform values of β and uniform electric current distributions. Here the voltage variation $V_x B_y z$ leads to a very nonuniform electric current distribution, and then the electromagnetic body forces lead to a very nonuniform distribution of β over the rotor-brush interface. Therefore we want the contact resistance for a single fiber rather than $R_c A_b$, and we want the normal tip force N_{trans} for the elastic-plastic transition of the contact spot rather than p_{trans} . The contact resistance for a single fiber is given by $(R_c A_b) n^*$, where n^* is given by equation (3), while $N_{trans} = p_{trans} / n^*$. Therefore the total resistance for a single fiber is

$$R_f = \frac{1}{\pi R^2} [(3.4 \times 10^{-9}) \beta^{-2/3} + \rho_e L]. \quad (6)$$

The electric current through each fiber from the stator to the rotor is given by

$$I = - \frac{\pi R^2 (\phi_0 + V_x B_y z)}{[(3.4 \times 10^{-9}) \beta^{-2/3} + \rho_e L]}, \quad (7)$$

where z is evaluated at the location of each fiber. For the single-fiber model, I appears in the dimensionless parameters,

$$\beta_x = \frac{I B_x L^3}{EI'}, \quad \beta_y = \frac{I B_y L^3}{EI'}, \quad \beta_z = \frac{I B_z L^3}{EI'}, \quad (8a-c)$$

where $I' = \pi R^4 / 4$ is the second moment of area of the fiber cross section. For copper, $N_{trans} = (1.5 \times 10^5) \pi R^2 [N]$. In the single-fiber model, the normal force N appears in the dimensionless parameter $v = NL^2 / EI'$, so $v_{trans} = (1.5 \times 10^5) \pi R^2 L^2 / EI'$ and $\beta = v / v_{trans}$. Note $\beta_x, \beta_y, \beta_z$, the components of the Lorentz force to fiber stiffness force are different from the unsubscripted β , which is the contact force to the elastic-plastic yield force.

IV. APPROACH

For the present basic brush, the only variation between fibers arises from the fact that the electric current through each fiber is a function of z , as indicated by equation (7). In other words, if $B_y = 0$, then there is no variation between fibers and β is uniform over the brush-rotor interface. We are only interested in cases with $B_y \neq 0$, so that there is a significant eddy current driven by the voltage variation $V_x B_y z$. There is no variation in x . At any specific value of z , the entire row of fibers for $-L_x \leq x \leq L_x$ behaves in the same way, while an adjacent row of fibers at another value of z may behave in a very different way from the first row. We divide $-L_z \leq z \leq L_z$ into NZ equal intervals with $\Delta z = 2L_z / NZ$. We can insure that each interval contains only one row of fibers by setting NZ equal to the number of rows of fibers across the z dimension of the brush. However this would be computationally wasteful if we can obtain accurate results with two or three rows of fibers in each z interval. We assume that all rows of fibers in one interval have the same values of $v, \beta_x, \beta_y, \beta_z$ and the same three-dimensional deformations. Since the only variation between fibers arises from the z variation of I in equation (7), we evaluate equation (7) at the midpoint of each interval,

$$z_k = -L_z + \left(K - \frac{1}{2}\right) \Delta z, \quad \text{for } K = 1 \text{ to } NZ. \quad (9)$$

We assume that what we are calling the stator is mounted on a spring, (1) which keeps the stator surface parallel to the rotor surface, (2) which allows motion of the stator surface in the y direction, and (3) which produces a specified normal force between the brush and the rotor surface. We represent the specified force by the average value of β , namely $\bar{\beta}$. With the z variation of I , the electromagnetic body forces push the tips of some fibers against the rotor surface and pull others away from the rotor surface, leading to a z variation of V . The dimensionless normal force on the tip of each fiber in the Δz centered at z_k is V_k . The specified force produced by the spring supporting the stator is represented by the condition

$$\sum_{K=1}^{NZ} V_K = NZ \times \bar{\beta} \times v_{trans}. \quad (10)$$

We apply the single-fiber model for the fibers in each of the NZ intervals. For each interval, the inputs to the single-fiber model

are $v_K, \beta_{xK}, \beta_{yK}, \beta_{zK}, \theta_0, \alpha_0$ and the outputs are $x_K(s), y_K(s), z_K(s)$. Here x_K, y_K, z_K are the local coordinates normalized by L , for each fiber in the K -th interval, while s is the dimensionless distance along the fiber from its root fixed into the stator at $s=0$ to its tip sliding along the rotor surface at $s=1$. With $y_{iK} = y_K(1)$ as the dimensionless y coordinate at the tip of each fiber in the K -th interval, the condition that the rotor and stator surfaces remain parallel is

$$y_{iK} = y_{i0}, \quad \text{for } K = 1 \text{ to } NZ, \quad (11)$$

where y_{i0} is an unknown constant which must be determined as part of the solution.

The electric current through each fiber in the K -th interval is given by equation (7) with $z = z_K$ and with $\beta = \beta_K = v_K / v_{trans}$. The electric current per unit area of the brush-rotor interface is In^* , where n^* is given by equation (3). Therefore the relationship between I_{trans} and ϕ_0 is

$$I_{trans} = -2L_x (\Delta z) v_f \sin \theta_0 \cos \alpha_0 \sum_{K=1}^{NZ} \frac{(\phi_0 + V_x B_y z_K)}{\left[(3.4 \times 10^{-9}) \beta_K^{-2/3} + \rho_e L \right]}. \quad (12)$$

The determination of the NZ values of $\beta_K = v_K / v_{trans}$ requires an iterative solution, and the value of ϕ_0 must be determined for each iteration from the equations

$$Q_1 = \sum_{K=1}^{NZ} \left[(3.4 \times 10^{-9}) \beta_K^{-2/3} + \rho_e L \right]^{-1}, \quad (13a)$$

$$Q_2 = \sum_{K=1}^{NZ} z_K \left[(3.4 \times 10^{-9}) \beta_K^{-2/3} + \rho_e L \right]^{-1}, \quad (13b)$$

$$\phi_0 = -\frac{1}{Q_1} \left[V_x B_y Q_2 + \frac{I_{trans}}{2L_x (\Delta z) v_f \sin \theta_0 \cos \alpha_0} \right]. \quad (13c)$$

Each iteration begins with estimates of the values of v_K for $K = 1$ to NZ , which satisfy equation (10). First, $\beta_K = v_K / v_{trans}$. Second, equations (13) determine ϕ_0 . Third, equation (7) with $z = z_K$ and $\beta = \beta_K$ gives the electric current I_K through each fiber in the K -th interval, so that equations (8) give the values of $\beta_{xK}, \beta_{yK}, \beta_{zK}$. Fourth, the single-fiber model is applied for each of the NZ intervals. The inputs are $v_K, \beta_{xK}, \beta_{yK}, \beta_{zK}, \theta_0, \alpha_0$ and the outputs are $x_K(s), y_K(s), z_K(s)$. The single-fiber model also requires an iterative solution, so that there are NZ single-fiber iterative solutions inside each brush iteration. For the iterative solution, the only output of interest is $y_{iK} = y_K(1)$. In general, the solution for each iteration is not the correct solution because the values of y_{iK} for $K = 1$ to NZ are not the same, so that the NZ conditions in equation (11) are not satisfied. The final steps in a brush iteration are the determination of improved estimates of the values of v_K for $K = 1$ to NZ , which satisfy equation (10). Here improved means that the next iteration using these

values of v_K leads to a smaller value of the error defined by

$$Error = \sum_{K=1}^{NZ} |y_{iK} - y_{i0}|. \quad (14)$$

In order to determine y_{i0} and the improved estimates of v_K , we assume a linear relationship between the correction to v_K and the error ($y_{i0} - y_{iK}$) for the K -th interval,

$$v_K^{(next)} = v_K + \kappa (y_{i0} - y_{iK}), \quad (15)$$

where κ is a constant. Since we want $v_K^{(next)}$ to satisfy equation (10), we introduce equation (15) into equation (10) and solve for y_{i0} ,

$$y_{i0} = \frac{1}{NZ} \sum_{K=1}^{NZ} y_{iK} + \frac{1}{\kappa} \left[\bar{\beta} v_{trans} - \frac{1}{NZ} \sum_{K=1}^{NZ} v_K \right]. \quad (16)$$

If the values of v_K satisfy equation (10), then y_{i0} is simply the average of the values of y_{iK} . The only reason the values of v_K for a given iteration would not satisfy equation (10) is that any negative value of v_K must be replaced by a small positive value, e.g., 10^{-14} , in order to compute the values of $\beta_K^{-2/3}$. We use equation (16) in order to insure that v_K satisfy equation (10) in the iteration after one where a negative value of v_K occurred. Once y_{i0} has been determined, the next set of estimates of v_K is given by equation (15). The numerical results to date have indicated that equation (15) may overestimate the correction to v_K when the fibers are severely loaded and the deformations are large. This overestimation leads to oscillations in the values of v_K and y_{i0} with successive iterations. Therefore we introduce a relaxation factor w , so that $v_K^{(next)} = v_K + w\kappa [y_{i0} - y_{iK}]$. (17) For small deformations, $w = 1$ leads to monotonic convergence of the brush iterations. For the large deformations discussed in the Results section, we found that $w=0.3$ eliminated oscillations between successive iterations and always led to a converged solution. The constant κ is an estimate of $\Delta v / \Delta y_i$. For one fiber configuration, an increase in v of one led to a decrease of y_i of -0.016, so that $\kappa = -62.5$.

The total Joulean heating in the brush is given by

$$2L_x (\Delta z) \sum_{K=1}^{NZ} (\phi_0 + V_x B_y z_K)^2 \left[(3.4 \times 10^{-9}) \beta_K^{-2/3} + \rho_e L \right]^{-1}. \quad (19)$$

V. SOME TYPICAL RESULTS

One case is discussed here in order to illustrate the capability of the brush model. The fibers are copper with $\rho_e = 1.7 \times 10^{-8} \Omega - m$ and $E = 1.2 \times 10^{11} Pa$. The dimensions are $R = 25 \mu m$, $L = 1.27 cm$, $L_x = 1.0 cm$, and $L_z = 0.5 cm$. The undeformed fibers are perpendicular to the rotor and stator

surfaces, i.e., $\theta_0 = \pi/2 \text{ rad}$ and $\alpha_0 = 0$, the fiber volume fraction $v_f = 0.17$, and the coefficient of sliding friction $\mu = 0.32$. We treat a brush with $V_x = 25 \text{ m/s}$, $B_x = 0$, $B_y = 1.1 \text{ T}$, $B_z = 0.7 \text{ T}$, $\bar{\beta} = 0.63$ and various values of the transport current, I_{trans} . Experience with the single-fiber model indicates that a history dependence is possible, so we follow a specific history. Throughout the history, $V_x = 25 \text{ m/s}$ and $B_x = 0$. We incrementally increase B_y, B_z and $\bar{\beta}$ with $I_{trans} = 0$:

(a) $B_y = B_z = 0.1k$, $\bar{\beta} = 0.09k$, $k = 1$ to 7 and then

(b) $B_z = 0.7 \text{ T}$, $\bar{\beta} = 0.63$, $B_y = 0.7 + 0.1k$, $k = 1$ to 4 . For our base state, $B_y = 1.1 \text{ T}$, $B_z = 0.7 \text{ T}$, $\bar{\beta} = 0.63$, $I_{trans} = 0$. From our base state, we vary I_{trans} with $B_y = 1.1 \text{ T}$, $B_z = 0.7 \text{ T}$, $\bar{\beta} = 0.63$. We

first increase I_{trans} from 0 to 350 A . We then decrease I_{trans} from 350 A to -350 A . Finally we increase I_{trans} from -350 A to 0 . For all these calculations $NZ = 40$ and $\kappa = -30$. The relaxation factor w is decreased from 1.0 as $B_y, B_z, \bar{\beta}$ are incrementally increased from 0 , and $w = 0.3$ for all the calculations for $B_y = 1.1 \text{ T}$, $B_z = 0.7 \text{ T}$, $\bar{\beta} = 0.63$. The

iterative single-fiber model with backward integration converges rapidly, generally reaching a relative error of 10^{-12} in 5-10 iterations. The number of brush iterations to achieve a relative error of 10^{-8} varies greatly. For the case considered here, a 10 A change in I_{trans} may lead to abrupt changes in the values of v_K and in the deformed shapes of some fibers, leading to significant changes for all the fibers through equation (10). For such abrupt changes, as many as 700 brush iterations were required to achieve convergence to eight significant figures. The number of integrations for single fibers is equal to the number of brush iterations times NZ times the number of single-fiber iterations. However 700 brush iterations with $NZ = 40$ takes several seconds on a standard PC. The present scheme for the determination of improved values of v_K at the end of each brush iteration is a very simple scheme. A Newton-Raphson scheme with $v_K^{(next)} = v_K + \Delta v_K$ and with the solution of linear equations for Δv_K might reduce the amount of computer time needed to achieve a given relative error.

First we consider the results for our base state with $I_{trans} = 0$. For this case, $\phi_0 = -58.16 \text{ mV}$, $y_{t0} = 0.9937$ and the Joulean heating is 30.355 W . This case involves only the eddy current, which is the local circulation of electric current through the brush, stator and rotor, driven by the voltage variation $V_x B_y z$. There is an electric current from the stator to the rotor through the fibers near $z = -L_z$ and an equal electric current from the rotor to the stator through the fibers near $z = L_z$. The frictional forces

μv_K pull all the fibers in the $+x$ direction. For the fibers near $z = -L_z$ with $I_K > 0$, the electromagnetic body force due to B_z pushes the fibers further into the $+x$ direction, thus bending them away from the rotor face and reducing the local values of β_K . For the fibers near $z = L_z$ with $I_K < 0$, the electromagnetic body force due to B_z pushes the fibers in the $-x$ direction, pushing them toward and beyond $x = 0$. These fibers are shoved into the rotor surface, increasing the local values of β_K . The plot of β versus z for this case is presented in Figure 2.

Here $0.073 \leq \beta \leq 4.72$. Clearly there is a large deviation from $\bar{\beta} = 0.63$. The voltage variation is linear in z , but the contact resistances for the fibers near $z = -L_z$ with small values of β_K are much larger than those for the fibers near $z = L_z$ with much larger values of β_K , so that the electric current distribution across the brush is far from linear. The plot of j_y , which is the electric current per unit area of the brush-rotor interface, is also shown in Figure 2. Here $-9.06 \text{ MA/m}^2 \leq j_y \leq 1.66 \text{ MA/m}^2$. The much smaller contact resistance near $z = L_z$ due to the large local values of β_K allows much more local electric current, and $\phi_0 = -58.16 \text{ mV}$ is needed to drive enough current from the stator to the rotor over the region with much larger contact resistance so that $I_{trans} = 0$.

Figure 2. Results for $I_{trans} = 0$: β and j_y versus z .

The x and z coordinates of the tips of the NZ “fibers” are plotted in Figure 3. We refer to all the fibers in the Δz centered at z_K as the K -th fiber. For all plots of x_t, z_t , $x_t = Lx(1)$ and $z_t = z_K + Lz(1)$, where $x(s), z(s)$ are the dimensionless local fiber coordinates. The fibers for $K = 1$ to 29 all have essentially the same values of x_t . These fibers all have $I_K > 0$, so that their electromagnetic body forces due to B_z push them in the $+x$ direction. As K increases from 1 to 29, I_K and the electromagnetic body forces due to B_z decrease, but β_K and the frictional forces in the $+x$ direction, $\mu \beta_K v_{trans}$ increase. The decrease in the electromagnetic body force is

balanced by the increase in the frictional force, leading to essentially the same values of x_t for $K = 1$ to 29. For $K = 30$ to 40, $I_K < 0$, so that the electromagnetic body forces due to B_z are in the $-x$ direction, and become very large as K approaches 40 and j_y approaches -9.06 MA/m^2 .

Figure 3. Results for $I_{trans}=0$: x and z coordinates of the fiber tips.

As K increases from 30, frictional forces in the $+x$ direction, $\mu\beta_k V_{trans}$, also increase. However, the electromagnetic body forces in the $-x$ direction have much larger increases, so that x_t decreases and $x_t < 0$ for $K = 38$ to 40. The values of z_t in Figure 3 are the result of the electromagnetic body forces due to $B_y = 1.1T$. The sign of the electromagnetic body force in the z direction due to B_y depends on the signs of both x_t and I_K . If $x_t > 0$ and $I_K > 0$, then the force is in the $+z$ direction, pushing all the fibers for $K = 1$ to 29 in the $+z$ direction. For $K = 30$ to 37, $x_t > 0$ and $I_K < 0$, so the electromagnetic body forces due to B_y push the fibers in the $-z$ direction. Figure 3 indicates that the fibers for $K = 35$ and 36 have almost equal values of z_t . Therefore the tips of the fibers in these two rows are touching. Fiber-fiber contact forces are neglected here, but will be included in a future brush model. For $K = 38$ to 40, $x_t < 0$ and $I_K < 0$, so that the electromagnetic body forces due to B_y push these fibers in the $+z$ direction. Therefore these rows are more spread apart than those near $K = 35$.

Next we increase I_{trans} from 0 to $350A$. Increments of $10A$ and $50A$ led to exactly the same results. For $I_{trans} = 350A$, $\phi_0 = -91.0mV$, $y_{t0} = 0.9704$ and the Joulean heating is $58.82W$. The plot of β versus z is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Results for: $I_{trans}=350A$, β and j_y versus z .

Here $0.186 \leq \beta \leq 5.02$. Compared to $I_{trans}=0$, the values of β are more uniform, except for $\beta_{40} = 5.02$. Clearly the $K=40$ fiber is behaving differently from the other 39 fibers. The plot of j_y versus z is also presented in Figure 4. Here, $-5.32 \text{ MA/m}^2 \leq j_y \leq 3.6 \text{ MA/m}^2$. For $K = 1$ to 33, $I_K > 0$ and for $K = 34$ to 40, $I_K < 0$. Even with a transport current of $350A$ from the stator to the rotor, the eddy current is strong enough to drive electric current from the rotor to the stator over roughly one-sixth of the brush. The values of x_t, z_t are plotted

in Figure 5. As K increases from 1 to 33, x_t actually increases slightly, indicating that the increases in the frictional forces are slightly larger than the decreases in the electromagnetic body forces due to B_z . For $K = 34$ to 40, $I_K < 0$, so that the electromagnetic body forces due to B_z are in the $-x$ direction.

However $x_t > 0$ for $K = 34$ to 39, and x_t is only negative for $K = 40$. This large change between $K = 39$ and 40 is illustrated by the plots of the local dimensionless fiber coordinates, $y(s)$ versus $x(s)$, for $K = 1, 39$ and 40, which are also presented in Figure 5. Again we note that the x_t, z_t in Figure 5 are dimensional brush coordinates, while the x, y in Figure 5 are dimensionless fiber coordinates.

Figure 5. Results for $I_{trans}=350A$ x and z coordinates of the fiber tips and plots of the dimensionless x and y coordinates along the deformed fibers for $K=1$, $K=39$ and $K=40$.

The transport current from the stator to the rotor interacts with B_z to produce electromagnetic body forces in the $+x$ direction, increasing the values of x_t for all the fibers, compared with the values for $I_{trans}=0$. For $K=39$, $j_y = -2.2MA/m^2$ with $I_{trans}=350A$, so that the electromagnetic body forces due to B_z are not large enough to overwhelm the frictional forces, and $x_t > 0$. Only for $K=40$, with $j_y = -5.3MA/m^2$, are the electromagnetic body forces due to B_z large enough to lead to $x_t < 0$.

For $K=34$ to 39 , $I_K < 0$ and $x_t > 0$, so that the electromagnetic body forces due to B_y are in the $-z$ direction. The magnitudes of these body forces in the $-z$ direction increase greatly as K increases from 34 to 39, as j_y decreases from 0 to $-2.2MA/m^2$, and as x_t only decreases from $0.27cm$ to $0.20cm$. With these body forces, the present model, which ignores fiber-fiber contact forces, predicts that the fibers pass through each other, e.g., z_t for $K=39$ is less than z_t for $K=38$. Of course, this is impossible, but the results clearly show that several rows of fibers are jammed together by the electromagnetic body forces due to B_y .

Next we decrease I_{trans} from $350A$ to 0. After every incremental decrease in I_{trans} , we obtained exactly the same results that we obtained with increasing I_{trans} . Therefore there is no history dependence or hysteresis for $I_{trans} > 0$.

Next we decrease I_{trans} from to $-350A$. With each $10A$ decrease in I_{trans} , another fiber snaps from a deformation with a large value of β and a double curvature to a deformation with a much smaller value of β and with single curvature: the $K=39$ fiber snaps back as I_{trans} is decreased from $-160A$ to $-170A$, the $K=38$ fiber snaps back as I_{trans} is decreased from $-170A$ to $-180A$, etc.

For $I_{trans} = -350A$, $\phi_0 = +93.86mV$, $y_{t0} = 0.9979$ and the Joulean heating is $36.62W$. The values of x_t, z_t for $I_{trans} = -350A$ are plotted in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Results for $I_{trans} = -350A$ with I_{trans} decreasing: x and z coordinates of the fiber tips and plots of the dimensionless x and y coordinates along the deformed fibers for $K=20$ and $K=21$.

Figure 7. Results for $I_{trans} = -350A$ with I_{trans} decreasing: β and j_y versus z.

All of the fibers for $K=21$ to 40 have snapped back, and $x_t = -0.077$ for all of these fibers. The values of y versus x for $K=20$ and $K=21$ are plotted in Figure 6 also. The $K=21$ fiber snapped back when I_{trans} was reduced from $-340A$ to $-350A$, while the $K=20$ fiber now has the maximum value of β and has the deformation with double curvature. The values of β versus z are plotted in Figure 7. Here, $0.032 \leq \beta \leq 3.83$, where the maximum value of β occurs at $K=20$. The values of j_y versus z are plotted in Figure 7 also.

Here $-9.58MA/m^2 \leq j_y \leq 0.583MA/m^2$ For $-0.5cm \leq z \leq -0.34cm$, there is a total current of $10A$ from the stator to the rotor, for $-0.34cm \leq z \leq 0$, there is a total current of $250A$ from the rotor to the stator, and for $0 \leq z \leq 0.5cm$, there is a total current of $110A$ from the rotor to the stator. The values of β in Figure 7 illustrate the extreme nonuniformity of the contact resistance over the brush-rotor interface, and the values of j_y in Figure 7 illustrate the effect of the nonuniform contact resistance on the distributions of the eddy and transport currents.

Next we increase I_{trans} back from $-350A$ to 0 . As I_{trans} was decreased from $-150A$ to $-350A$, the fibers for $K = 21$ to 40 snapped back. As we increase I_{trans} from $-350A$, so that the electromagnetic body forces in the $-x$ direction due to B_z decrease in magnitude, we do not expect each fiber to reverse the abrupt change in deformation at the same value of I_{trans} . Experience with the single-fiber model indicates that there is some hysteresis associated with these abrupt changes in fiber deformation. We increased I_{trans} from $-350A$ with increments of $10A$. With I_{trans} increasing, the $K = 21$ fiber is the first to be pulled abruptly forward to a deformation with double curvature, and there is a large increase in β_{21} . Before the abrupt change, the fiber is bent into the $-x$ direction and has a small value of β . The abrupt change occurs because the fiber tip digs into the rotor surface which is moving in the $+x$ direction. This leads to abrupt increases in β and in the frictional force in the $+x$ direction at the tip. It also leads to an abrupt decrease in the contact resistance, so that the distributed electromagnetic body force in the $-x$ direction due to B_z also has a dramatic increase in magnitude. The competition between the two large forces leads to a deformation with double curvature. As we increase I_{trans} , successive fibers are snagged by the moving rotor surface and pulled into deformations with double curvature at intervals of $17-18A$, while they had snapped back at intervals of $10A$ when I_{trans} was decreasing.

When we increased I_{trans} from $-350A$ to $-150A$, the $K = 21$ to 32 fibers were snagged by the rotor surface, leading to larger values of β . With I_{trans} varying back and forth between $\pm 350A$, there is a hysteresis for $I_{trans} < 0$, but there is none for $I_{trans} > 0$. This hysteresis is the result of successive fibers snapping backward with abrupt decreases in β as I_{trans} is decreased from $-150A$ to $-350A$, and of successive fibers being snagged by the moving rotor surface with abrupt increases in β as I_{trans} is increased from $-350A$ to 0 .

The values of ϕ_0 versus I_{trans} are plotted in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Electric Potential ϕ_0 versus Transport Current for increasing and decreasing I_{trans} .

For $I_{trans} > 0$, this plot is essentially a straight line. For $I_{trans} < 0$ with I_{trans} decreasing, this plot is composed of two straight lines with an abrupt change of slope at $I_{trans} = -150A$. For $I_{trans} < 0$ with I_{trans} increasing, this plot is a curve with an abrupt change of slope at $I_{trans} = 0$. The values of the Joulean heating versus I_{trans} are plotted in Figure 9. The values of the Joulean heating are $30.355W$ for $I_{trans} = 0$, $58.825W$ for $I_{trans} = 350A$, and $36.617W$ for $I_{trans} = -350A$. For I_{trans} decreasing, the minimum Joulean heating is $26.39W$ for $I_{trans} = -190A$, and for I_{trans} increasing, the minimum Joulean heating is $27.68W$ for $I_{trans} = -120A$.

Figure 9. Joulean Heating versus Transport Current for increasing and decreasing I_{trans} .

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In a previous study we derived the formalism for analyzing the electromechanics of a single, current carrying fiber sliding against a plane in the presence of a large magnetic field of arbitrary orientation. In that study, the current and the mechanical contact force at the fiber tip-slider interface are specified and do not change but the fiber itself, changes shape, deflects and the applied electric potential necessary to drive the current varies with conditions such as slider speed and differing magnetic field conditions. We discovered a bifurcation in the solution space of such fibers which leads to a history dependant equilibrium condition.

In the present paper we have extended that investigation to include a collection of fibers that carry a constant total transport current and are held against the slider by a constant total force. The currents and tip forces of the individual fibers are allowed to vary but the sum of the electrical currents and forces over all of the fibers remains constant. First we find tremendous variation of fiber tip contact forces and currents among the collection of fibers even though the average load and total transport current remain constant. We find that the hysteretic behavior seen in the single fiber investigation carries over to the collection of fibers with additional phenomena occurring. Because the slider cuts flux, a potential gradient exists across the slider face and therefore between the fibers of the collection and circulating currents between the fibers result. These currents are in opposite directions on opposite sides of the collection and we have oppositely directed Lorentz forces on the collection causing individual fibers to move either with rotation, against rotation or perpendicular to rotation. These effects are altered by the direction of the transport current and hysteresis is seen in both the Joulean heating and the contact potential necessary to drive the transport current.

It is known that wear in fiber brushes is a highly non-linear function of the normal load² and many previous studies^{8, 9, 10, 11} report that wear depends on the direction of current. The present investigation will be extended in a future study by incorporating both fiber-fiber interactions and the effects of wear. In that study we may expect that the individual fibers carrying the most mechanical load and current will wear the fastest but the overall behavior of the collection may not be so simple because of nonlinear and hysteretic effects.

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IX. BIOGRAPHIES

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